

Novel nutrient extraction to increase power for microbial fuel cells

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Abstract—We present experimental data showing how the power output of a sediment microbial fuel cell (MFC) can be dramatically increased by recirculating a dilute 1% mud solution between a settling tank and anode chamber with and without carbon granules. This enables both greater power output and MFC operation out of the mud. With carbon granules added to the bottom of the 125 ml anode chamber, power outputs of 1.3 mW were achieved with total anode surface areas of 77 cm² (graphite chips) and an anode displaced volume of 31 cc. This equates to a volumetric energy density of 1.2 W per ft³ of anode volume.

Keywords—flow circulation, carbon granules, anode chamber, sediment, pumping

I. INTRODUCTION

Microbial fuel cells (MFC's) are typically buried inches deep in the sediment and harvest energy by exploiting a voltage difference between their buried anodes (roughly -0.4 V) and seawater exposed cathodes (roughly +0.3 V). Though conceptually and mechanically simple, buried anodes require some undersea deployment scheme to implant the anodes within the sediment.

To overcome this limitation of buried MFC's, we demonstrate how an MFC anode chamber can operate while resting on or even detached from the sediment surface, relying only on intermittent and slow circulation of a dilute 1% mud solution between a settling tank and anode chamber. The transfer of sediment from ocean floor into a settling or capture tank of an MFC can be done through many methods and is the subject of a Navy patent.

Immersed sediment MFC's are limited by diffusion driven transport of organic nutrients to anode surfaces. Thus, a significant increase in MFC power output can be gained by pumping nutrients through an anode chamber as demonstrated by: Reimers [1]—who used flow from a cold seep to drive sediment pore water into a bottom resting anode chamber, and Liu [2]—who pumped pore water through a surface resting, mud filled anode chamber. Both methods transferred sediment nutrients into an anode chamber via pore water transport, resulting in greater power than diffusion reliant MFC's.

In this paper, we describe how increased power was achieved by extracting and then concentrating sediment

nutrients about the anodes by circulating a dilute mud solution between a settling tank and anode chamber (patent pending). This paper will describe the test setup and results for that demonstration.

II. TEST SETUP

Fig. 1 shows key elements of the experiment: 1) peristaltic pump slowly recirculates mud solution between settling tank and anode chamber inside seawater tank, 2) settling holds 1L of 1-2% mud in seawater solution, 3) sealed anode chamber rests on mud bottom of 15 gal acrylic tank and contains four anode chips and carbon granules at chamber bottom, 4) cathode “teabag” consisting of a carbon cloth wrapped and sewn around carbon granules.

Fig. 1 Test set up to evaluate effects of slow recirculation of 1-2% mud solution between settling tank and anode chamber with and without carbon granules at chamber bottom.

A 1-2% mud solution was first loaded into a 1 liter settling chamber to allow for mud particles to fall out of suspension and to reduce dissolved oxygen content through mud exposure. Dissolved oxygen content was typically reduced to below 1% within 24 hrs as measured by an oxygen sensor probe integrated within the settling chamber [3]. The settling chamber also had inlet/outlet ports to enable flow recirculation to/from the anode chamber.

Figure 2 shows that the anode chamber consisted of a 125 ml plastic jar (2-3/4" Base Diameter, 2-3/8" Height) and a lid equipped with four tube fittings: two for flow inlet/out ports,

a third for a potted wiring port and a fourth fitting to be filled with a gelatin salt bridge for hydrogen ion exchange with the ambient seawater. Suspended from the lid within the jar was a four chip (graphite) anode array which was ganged to a single wire passing thru the lid. Each chip measured 1" (2.5 cm) x 1.5" (3.8 cm) x 1/8" (0.3 cm) and was racked on an awl thread in 1/4" (0.6 cm) intervals using nuts/washer on both sides of the chip. For the four chips ganged together, the total anode surface area was 12 in² (77 cm²) and the total displaced volume was 1.9 in³ (31 cc).

Fig. 2. Anode chamber with tube fittings in lid and four graphite anode chips suspended under lid.

After allowing for oxygen reduction in the settling tank, the solution was circulated continuously through the anode chamber at a rate of 125 ml per day (one chamber volume per day). This slow recirculation was performed continuously until stable open circuit (OC) conditions were achieved with: roughly (-) 400 mV on the anode and (+) 300 mV on the cathode as referenced to a Ag/AgCl reference electrode. After stable OC conditions were achieved, the pumping was stopped and a 100,000 ohm resistor was connected across the anode and cathode to slowly open up current flow. Lower ohm resistors were successively applied to maintain a 400 mV voltage (Whole Cell) potential between anode and cathode.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Through the inlet/outlet tube connections at the top of the lid, the anode chamber was exposed to the oxygen reduced mud solution flow in three ways: a) No flow or static immersion, b) slow recirculation over the anodes at a rate of 1 anode chamber volume (125 ml)/day, and c) slow recirculation over the anodes with carbon granules at chamber bottom.

With static immersion, negligible power was produced as there was no transport of the dilute nutrient solution across the anodes. However, slow pumping and slow pumping with granules at chamber bottom produced favorable results which will be discussed in greater detail.

Figure 3 shows the benefits of slowly pumping a dilute nutrient solution across an anode array. Here, three periods of slow pumping from Jan – March 2014 are plotted and show aggregate power from the four bare anode chips during pumping and after pumping is stopped. Examination of the power spikes after pump termination shows a growing “memory effect” or an increasing sustainment of high power after pumping is stopped. In Period 1, pumping is stopped at Day 21 and power output immediately plunges. However in Period 2, pumping is terminated at Day 37 and high power is retained up to approximately Day 54 or 14 days after pumping is stopped. Then in Period 3, pumping is terminated around Day 57 and the power boost is retained until Day 64 or 7 days after pumping is stopped. This sustainment of high power output after a pumping stop shows that microbial growth is being accelerated and sustained via pumping. This effect is similar to what the authors observed in their 2012 OCEANS paper [2].

Fig. 3. Effects of slow nutrient pumping across four graphite chip anodes in anode chamber (no granules at bottom)

Figure 4 shows effects of slow pumping across bare anodes with a layer of carbon granules at the bottom of the chamber (~30% of chamber height, reaching bottom of anode chips). Results show 2.1 mW peak output and an average 1.3 mW output from Days 10-20 after pump shutdown.

We speculate that increased power output is due to nutrient accumulation in the carbon granules. Future experiments will apply different pumping and filtering techniques to capture organic nutrients on carbon granules deposited in between anodes.

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Fig. 4. Effects of slow nutrient pumping across four graphite chip anodes with carbon granules at bottom of anode chamber.